

Systematic Alarm Flood Reduction

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Abstract: The introduction of distributed control systems and the high level of interconnectivity of modern process plants has caused alarm flooding to become one of the main problems in alarm management of process plants. A reduction of alarm flood periods contributes to a decrease in plant incidents. In this work, a combination of alarm log, process data and connectivity analysis is used to isolate consequence alarms originating from the same process abnormality and to provide a causal alarm suggestion. The effectiveness of the method is illustrated on an industrial case study of an ethylene plant, a typical example of a large-scale industrial system. This technical work was influenced by the discussions and work done over the years while collaborating with Nina Thornhill.

Keywords: Alarm systems, fault detection and diagnosis, root-cause, plant-wide disturbance, plant connectivity, approximate sequence matching, large-scale systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

The accident at the Milford Haven refinery in 1994 and the legal prosecution that followed triggered a lot of interest in alarm management. The pioneering work from Bransby and Jenkinson was published 5 years later (Bransby, Jenkinson, 1999) and heavily influenced following best practice documents such as EEMUA 191, ISA 18.1 and IEC 62682. Alarm management and the theory behind in this era was mainly coined by industrial practitioners. The time consuming and expensive alarm rationalization process was – and in many respects still is – the main obstacle on the way towards plants with high quality alarm systems (Hollender et al., 2016). Systematic methods based on available data sources promise to automate the alarm rationalization process more and make it therefore more affordable. Together with Nina Thornhill and Alexander Fay, ABB set up a research project to investigate if and how standard Process and Instrumentation Diagrams (P&ID) can be used to support alarm systems. During that project we experienced once more one of the main obstacles for academic alarm management research: alarm data and the required context are hard to get from relevant industrial plants. After having finally found a plant willing to share their P&IDs and their alarm logs and while we were sitting in its control room, we could not help but notice alarms kept ringing in one after the other. Surprisingly, the operating team was extremely relaxed and didn't even seem to notice the alarms. It turned out that the plant was so highly automated, that the control room was most of the time unmanned. Fortunately, we were later able to find another plant and the work resulted in a very nice paper (Schleburg, Christiansen, Fay and Thornhill, 2013).

Alarm systems are crucial elements in the operation of process plants as they continuously monitor the process and inform the operators if an undesired process state requires

their assessment or if an action is required (IEC-62682, 2014). The introduction of distributed control systems in the process industry has increased the number of alarms per operator exponentially. Additionally, nowadays, modern process plants present a high level of interconnectivity due to steam recirculation, heat integration and to the use of complex control systems. A disturbance affecting the process plant can therefore spread through its material, energy and information connections and affect all the process variables on the path. Alarms associated to these process variables are triggered and may overload the control room operators who will not be able to properly investigate each of these alarms (Wang et al., 2015). This undesired situation known as alarm flood has been recognized as a major cause of most industrial incidents investigated by the US Chemical Safety Board. IEC 62682 (2014) defines an alarm flood as the occurrence of more than 10 alarms per 10 minutes and per operator. In such situation, the operators might not be able to keep the process plant within safe operation endangering human lives and the environment (Bransby and Jenkinson, 1998). In a typical alarm log, a significant part of nuisance alarms falls in the following categories: repetitive alarms, standing alarms and consequence alarms. These techniques succeed in lowering the number of alarms when the process is running under nominal conditions. Nevertheless, if an abnormality occurs and propagates through the plant, these methods are unable to suppress consequence alarms and to provide a proper diagnosis. This task demands to identify all causal relations between alarms (Hollender and Beuthel, 2007). On the other hand, noticing that a large portion of the alarms occurring in an alarm flood are related to each other and follow a specific pattern, Kabir et al. (2013) and Cheng et al. (2013) suggest using sequence pattern matching for grouping consequence alarms. Kabir et al. (2013) presented a method in which the similarity between alarm flood sequences is determined under the assumption that alarms occur in a consequential manner.

This assumption may however not always be true as the order of occurrence of alarms is highly dependent on their limit setting. Postulating that the exact order of alarm occurrences is not as important as their proximity in time, Cheng et al. (2013) proposed an alternative method for pattern matching of alarm flood sequences based on the Smith-Waterman algorithm. Time stamps of the alarms present in the alarm flood sequence are used to blur the order of the alarm sequence when the alarm time stamps are considered close to each other.

Schleburg et al. (2013) suggest a method to group consequence alarms based on both a topology model describing the process connectivity and a set of rules built using process knowledge. In this method, every pair of alarms is checked against the set of rules and the plant connectivity to evaluate if two alarms are related. While grouping related alarms has a clear benefit in assisting the operators reacting to an alarm flood episode, pointing them to the causal alarm (i.e. the alarm related to the root-cause of the alarm flood) could significantly reduce their reaction time. Causal root-cause analysis for process troubleshooting is the topic of several recent contributions investigating the design of systematic methods for abnormality propagation paths determination and plant-wide disturbances causal analysis. Quantitative data-driven methods detecting directionality between measurements have emerged, such as time delay analysis (Fan and Deyun, 2012) or transfer entropy, which is used to identify the causality between measurements even in absence of observable time delays between them (Bauer et al., 2007). A combination of quantitative process history methods and qualitative models like Signed direct graphs (SDG) (Fan and Deyun, 2012) are proposed in Thambirajah et al. (2009).

The present work was strongly influenced by Nina Thornhill's ideas and follows the line of thought of Schleburg et al. (2013). It aims at developing a systematic method for the isolation of the causal alarm in an alarm flood. The proposed approach relies on the use of multiple process information sources: alarm logs, historical process data and a topology model of the process. Even though the data originating from different information sources differ in their nature, they are related to each other. By combining alarm log, process data and connectivity analysis not only related alarms triggering during an alarm flood can be grouped, but also their causal alarm can be identified.

2. CAUSAL ANALYSIS FOR ALARM FLOOD REDUCTION

The proposed approach for a causal analysis for alarm flood reduction relies on two assumptions:

- Alarm floods are the result of an abnormality propagating in the process through material, energy and information connections.
- If two alarm flood sequences are similar, they stem from the same process abnormality.

Regarding the first hypothesis, the objective is to reduce alarm floods caused by a disturbance spreading through the plant due to its high level of interconnectivity. As for the second hypothesis, if two alarm flood sequences share a common pattern and if a large portion of the alarm occurrences in the alarm floods are present in this pattern, it is very likely that they originate from the same process abnormality.

The proposed method consists of five steps (Rodrigo et al. 2017). In the first step, chattering alarms are removed from the alarm log. In the second step, time intervals containing alarm floods are identified and alarm flood sequences are built. Similar alarm flood sequences are clustered in the third step. In the fourth step, the signals and assets associated with the analyzed alarms are identified. In the last step, process data causal analysis followed by connectivity validation are performed in order to suggest a causal alarm.

2.1 Remove chattering alarms

Chattering alarms are defined by the industrial standard IEC 62682 (2014) as "alarms that repeatedly transition between the alarm state and the normal state in a short period of time". Since the present work focuses on analyzing consequence alarms, chattering alarms are removed prior to the causal analysis. Following Kabir et al. (2013), in order to remove chattering alarms, a minimal admissible time interval length is chosen and if the time elapsed between the occurrences of two alarms of the same type is lower than the chosen interval, the second alarm is removed. The minimal admissible time interval length in the present work is taken as 10 min, based on the definition of alarm flood.

2.2 Identify alarm flood periods

This step isolates time periods where alarm floods occur and builds the corresponding alarm flood sequences. The alarm log is divided into time intervals of 10 min. Intervals with more alarm occurrences than a specified threshold are highlighted. The threshold is chosen based on the definition of an alarm flood, i.e. more than 10 alarms per 10 min and per operator. Duration of alarm floods in process plants ranges from a few minutes to several hours. In order to identify an alarm flood regardless of its duration, consecutive intervals with more alarm occurrences than the specified threshold are merged. Since the alarm log is discretized, it might happen that the beginning or the end of an alarm flood sequence is cut out, in order not to lose part of the sequence, the time intervals before and after the consecutive time intervals containing more than alarms are also included.

2.3 Cluster alarm flood sequences

Once the alarm flood time intervals are isolated and the alarm flood sequences are built, similar alarm flood sequences are clustered using sequence pattern matching. Alarm time stamps are taken into account as the proximity in time of the alarms is more important than the exact order of occurrence. We use the method described in Cheng et al. (2013) based on a modified Smith-Waterman (MSW) algorithm to blur the order of the alarms in the sequence when they occur closely

Fig 1. Process and Instrumentation Diagram of the plant section under analysis.

in time. A similarity matrix is built using pairwise similarity indices obtained from the MSW algorithm. Finally, agglomerative hierarchical clustering (AHC) with the average linkage criterion is applied to cluster the alarm flood sequences. One main disadvantage of the MSW algorithm is its heavy computational burden. In order to overcome this problem a prefiltering stage is added. A less precise but less time-consuming method is used (Kabir et al., 2013). Combinations of alarm sequences with low similarity are filtered out and the MSW index computation is applied to a subset of alarm sequence combinations with a significant similarity. A pair of alarm sequences is considered similar if the two alarm sequences have a high ratio of alarms in common. If two alarm sequences have few alarms in common, the computation of the MSW similarity index is discarded.

2.4 Map alarms to signals and assets

The absence of a common naming convention for alarm, signal and assets tags hinders a straightforward mapping between the different process information sources. We propose to map alarms, signals and assets based on the similarity of the symbols contained in their tag names. For instance, the tag name of a temperature controller from the case study is TC11 in the P&ID, this controller has a signal

associated whose tag is TC11CO.XAY and an alarm type TC11CO is assigned to this signal.

2.5 Isolate the causal alarm

The first alarm with respect to the time of occurrence cannot be considered as the causal alarm since the time at which an alarm triggers is highly dependent on the settings of the alarm limits. Moreover, the time between the occurrence of a process abnormality and the corresponding alarm triggering is probabilistic. As the causal relationships between signals can be captured, the process data associated to these alarms should be analyzed instead. The method used for this purpose is transfer entropy (Bauer et al., 2007). Transfer entropy uses transition probabilities to estimate the amount of information transferred from one signal x to another signal y . The causality is obtained by comparing the amount of information transferred from signal x to signal y with the amount information transferred from signal y to signal x . This method may give rise to spurious results (Bauer et al., 2007). In order to reduce their number, the obtained results are validated against the plant connectivity information contained in the topology model of the plant. CAEX (Computer Aided Engineering eXchange) is a vendor independent object-oriented data exchange format based on the XML schema that has been used in the past years for structuring plant topology models in a flexible and expandable way (see e.g.:

Schleburg et al., 2013). The topology-based validation of the data-driven analysis starts with the identification of the assets corresponding to the alarms in the fault template. The connectivity of the plant is explored using a graph-search algorithm on a graph capturing the connections between assets in the plant. The depth first search algorithm is employed in this work. The assets suggested as root-causes from the data-driven analysis are taken as starting points of the disturbance propagation path while the remaining assets are taken as secondary disturbed elements. All feasible propagation paths between the suggested root-cause and each of the secondary disturbed assets are explored. If no feasible path is found, the root-cause hypothesis is discarded. Once the spurious results of the data-driven analysis have been filtered out and one of the root-cause suggestions has been validated with plant connectivity, the causal alarm is taken as the alarm associated to the root-cause asset.

3. INDUSTRIAL CASE STUDY

The proposed method determining the causal alarm in alarm flood sequence is illustrated by an analysis conducted on the cracking and quenching section of an ethylene plant located in Austria. The alarm management system of the plant has more than 3800 alarms configured in the monitoring system.

The analysis is performed using eight months of collected alarm data, during which more than 48000 alarms occurred. The process data is presented in an excel table with a one-second sampling period data set. A CAEX file containing the topology model of the plant is used. The P&ID of the plant section is shown in Fig. 1. The data are analyzed using a developed prototype software tool that guides the user through the steps of the proposed method.

After loading the alarm log to the software tool and performing the steps Remove chattering alarms and identify alarm flood periods, 23 alarm flood periods are identified. analyzed, four do not belong to any cluster and 19 are clustered under one of the three groups. Each one of these clusters containing similar alarm flood sequences represents a different process abnormality.

The process abnormality from Cluster1 is further analyzed. To perform the data-driven and connectivity analysis, the signals and assets associated to the alarms included in the template are identified. After loading the process data and the topology model of the plant, the automatic mapping using the Smith-Waterman algorithm is performed (analysis results are shown in Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Results of the clustering algorithm with details of two alarm sequences belonging to Cluster 1

Figure 3. Root-cause validation alarm flood sequences of Cluster 1 using process topology.

Finally, the result of the process-data analysis is validated using the process connectivity (Fig. 3). The process connectivity analysis found feasible propagation paths starting from the obtained propagation paths. The process connectivity analysis suggests that the abnormality spread from the pressure controller PC11 S to the valves G01 and G02 via the information connection between this controller and the valves. From valve G01, the disturbance spread to the pressure controller PC12 S. Simultaneously, the disturbance reached Cracking Zone A, Cracking Zone B, Cracking Zone C and Cracking Zone D via the heat exchangers LQE 1, LQE 2, LQE 3 and LQE 4. Sensors PI13 S, PI14 S, PI15 S and PI16 S were also affected by the propagating disturbance since they are located in the coils of the different cracking zones. The root-cause suggestion from the data-driven analysis is therefore validated by the plant connectivity analysis. An alarm associated to PC11 S is the given causal alarm suggestion, i.e. alarm PC11 CO 4. All the alarms in the

template will be grouped under it. After discussion with site engineers the obtained results were confirmed. The analyzed abnormal situation corresponds to a shift in the operating mode between cracking-decoking. The transition between these two operating modes triggers a characteristic alarm flood sequence. The site crew mentioned that pressure controller PC11 is performing the opening and closing of both valve G01 and valve G02 during the change of operation mode and is therefore the origin of the alarm flood.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Alarm flooding can be reduced by using a combination of data from different information sources. Combining alarm log, historical process data and process connectivity analysis allowed to not only group consequence alarms, but also to determine the causal alarm of an alarm flood sequence. The proposed method was tested on actual data collected from an ethylene plant. There is still a long way to go to put systematic alarm management into industrial practice.

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